

Grant Agreement No: 101004761

AIDAinnova

Advancement and Innovation for Detectors at Accelerators

Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures project AIDAINNOVA

DELIVERABLE REPORT

ACTS TRACKING ALGORITHMS

DELIVERABLE: D12.3

Document identifier:	AIDAinnova_D12.3
Due date of deliverable:	End of Month 43 (October 2024)
Report release date:	05/11/2024
Work package:	WP12: Software for Future Detectors
Lead beneficiary:	CNRS
Document status:	Final

Abstract:

During the AIDAinnova project, the Acts track reconstruction toolkit received many improvements contributed by participating institutes, ranging from core infrastructure consolidation to new tracking algorithms. Thanks to these developments, the Acts track reconstruction chain now features all the major components that one would expect to find inside of the track reconstruction pipeline of a typical HEP experiment. In parallel, R&D was carried out on dedicated projects to investigate the architectural changes needed to make Acts more amenable to GPU computing; the lessons learned from these investigations are now in the process of being integrated back into Acts. Finally, in another R&D area, new machine-learning based algorithms were devised for the purpose of simulating micro-patterned gaseous detectors (MPGDs) and reconstructing their signal.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2024

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

The Advancement and Innovation for Detectors at Accelerators (AIDAinnova) project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101004761. AIDAinnova began in April 2021 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	H. Grasland , M. Scodeggio	[IJCLAB,INFN-FE]	16/10/2024
Edited by	H.Grasland	[IJCLAB]	16/10/2024
Reviewed by	G.Stewart [WP coordinator] F.Gaede [WP coordinator]	[CERN] [DESY]	30/10/2024
Approved by	Paolo Giacomelli [Scientific coordinator] Steering Committee		05/11/2024

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION.....	4
2. CORE ACTS IMPROVEMENTS.....	5
2.1. COPING WITH GROWTH	5
2.2. IMPROVING EXPERIMENT INTEGRATION	7
2.3. ALGORITHMIC DEVELOPMENTS.....	8
3. ACTS GPU AND LINEAR ALGEBRA R&D.....	9
3.1. GPU TRACKING	9
3.2. LINEAR ALGEBRA SPEEDUP.....	10
4. MACHINE LEARNING FOR MPGDS.....	11
5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK.....	12
6. REFERENCES.....	13
ANNEX: GLOSSARY	16

Executive summary

AIDAinnova task 12.3 focused on track reconstruction, a key step of the process of transforming detector output into scientific knowledge. Improvements were carried out along three axes.

First, the Acts generic track reconstruction toolkit was enhanced to improve its long-term sustainability, make it more usable by physics experiments, increase coverage of classic tracking algorithms, and explore new algorithmic directions.

Second, R&D was carried out to evaluate how the Acts software architecture should evolve in order to better support Graphics Processing Units (GPUs). As a side effect, a possible path to improving Acts' linear algebra dependencies was investigated.

Finally, parametric simulation and track reconstruction code for micro-patterned gaseous detectors (MPGDs) was extended to support a new detector, the micro-resistive well (μ -RWELL), and to evaluate a new approach to cluster reconstruction with higher background resilience.

1. INTRODUCTION

To extract physical meaning from the signals of particle detectors, complex computations must be run over large amounts of experiment data. AIDAinnova task 12.3 specifically focuses on the reconstruction of the tracks of charged particles within the detector.

Historically, each particle physics experiment would maintain its own dedicated software to perform this task. However, this requires a large amount of person-power, with high redundancy across experiments since most track reconstruction codebases use very similar algorithms.

As a result, recent years have seen the emergence of generic track reconstruction toolkits that can be readily adopted by new physics experiments at a much reduced adoption cost, enabling sharing of both initial development effort and subsequent improvements. One of the most advanced projects in this area is the Acts toolkit [1]; we have therefore chosen to focus most effort on this project during the AIDAinnova project.

Specifically, members of task 12.3 focused on three areas of concern:

- Improving the fitness of Acts for use by experiments through a mixture of infrastructure consolidation, increased interoperability, and new algorithmic developments.
- Evaluating what changes to the core Acts abstractions would be needed to allow data processing on new hardware architectures like GPUs.
- Investigating new machine learning based approaches for track reconstruction in Multi-Patterned Gaseous Detectors (MPGDs).

The last two R&D studies were not directly performed in Acts, but in standalone codebases. However, the process of integrating the GPU R&D back into Acts has begun as of the end of 2024.

2. CORE ACTS IMPROVEMENTS

During the AIDAInnova project, the Acts project received many major code contributions, most of which can be categorized in three categories:

- keeping the project’s foundations solid, so that it remains maintainable in the future;
- improving integration with experiments’ geometry toolkits and event data models;
- adding more tracking algorithms, either to improve feature parity with existing codebases or to explore new techniques, such as machine learning approaches.

In the following sections we will cover the outcome of these developments in more detail.

2.1. COPING WITH GROWTH

As the Acts project grew and became integrated in increasingly large HEP experiments, some of its development practices had to scale up accordingly for the project to remain manageable.

One example of an area where these growing pains were felt early on is the Acts build process, which hit the resource limits of GitHub’s Continuous Integration (CI) runners, resulting in an unusable CI. This was caused by excessive usage of C++ templates, leading to a combinatorial explosion of the amount of code compiled in higher-level compilation units.

Figure 1: Web dashboard developed to visualize the highest-priority areas for build overhead optimization and the positive/negative impact of code changes on these areas of concern.

To resolve this problem, the Acts team first developed a web dashboard to easily visualise the heaviest compilation units and build-time impact of code changes (fig. 1), and then took action by strategically injecting dynamic dispatch points and moving functions to dedicated compilation units at higher-level interfaces so as to maximise the impact on the compilation overhead to minimise the impact on runtime performance.

Another aspect of Acts that hit its scalability limit during AIDAInnova was the physics validation process. Historically, physics validation was performed by running a set of C++ binaries that also served as usage examples for new users of the library. These binaries, controlled via command-line

options, would perform tasks such as generating data through Geant4 [2][3][4], mapping material to sensitive surfaces, or running various steps of the track reconstruction pipeline. Physics validation could then be performed by either analysing the output data files manually or by automatically checking for absence of changes with respect to a known-good state.

But this process broke down as the project scaled up. Firstly, as the C++ binaries were used in a rapidly growing number of configurations, the number of command-line options and interactions between them grew unmanageably large through a combinatorial explosion. The solution was the replacement of these binaries with more flexible Python bindings that enabled free-form scripting.

Figure 2: Physmon, a physics validation reporting system integrated inside of Acts pull requests.

Later, the number of validation scenarios also grew so large that even visualizing their output became a time-consuming chore. This was addressed by developing “physmon” (fig. 2), an automated physics performance report integrated into a GitHub pull request that enabled easy visualization of the physics performance outcome of pull requests.

There have been many other smaller-scale examples of Acts changes carried out during AIDAInnova that aimed at improving long-term project sustainability in the face of growth, ranging from the addition of new static analysis tools (e.g., SonarQube) to that of new testing workflows (e.g., Athena test builds to make sure Acts changes do not break ATLAS software; CI on GPUs).

2.2. IMPROVING EXPERIMENT INTEGRATION

As a cross-experiment toolkit, Acts must cope with the wide diversity of schemes used by HEP experiments to model their detector geometry and to encode detector data. While full plug-and-play operation is probably out of reach in the presence of such diversity, several areas of improvements were identified and improved upon during AIDAinnova.

Historically, using Acts together with DD4hep required the DD4hep geometry-building code to link against Acts (or later an Acts-provided shim library) and to extend its geometry with several Acts-specific extensions. This burden was reduced through contributions to DD4hep and changes to Acts that made it possible to express most of the Acts-required metadata using DD4hep abstractions.

The main remaining impedance mismatch is the Acts concept of detector layer, a group of surfaces used during track navigation, which DD4hep does not have. In fact it was realised during the detray GPU R&D, which will be discussed later, that this concept can be removed entirely which simplifies the Acts geometry model. Work to do so has been underway since, however this is still ongoing as detector geometry is one of the most central abstractions of a track reconstruction toolkit and modifications in this area affect many other components of Acts.

Other common geometry descriptions were not neglected either, as Acts gained the ability to import many new detector geometry concepts from GDML (Geant4) and GeoModel (most notably used by ATLAS ITk). AIDAinnova also saw the introduction of an SVG export feature for visualizing detector elements (fig. 3), which is very useful when debugging imported geometries. It was improved throughout the project, and later extended to the detray GPU R&D.

Figure 3: Example of detector element SVG visualization from Acts

Besides geometry, another critical interface between experiment software and Acts is the event data model (EDM), which is used to feed detector data into Acts and extract reconstructed tracks from Acts.

On the input side of this interface, AIDAInnova introduced support for the PODIO/EDM4hep toolkit, thus permitting better integration of Acts into the Turnkey Software Stack developed by AIDAInnova task 12.2. The Generic MultiTrajectory storage system was also introduced to help Acts interoperate better with experiment-specific data formats like xAOD from ATLAS. Following memory usage concerns, the measurement storage layout was also made more compact.

On the output side a public track event data model was introduced about halfway through AIDAInnova, which was then refined throughout the rest of the project.

2.3. ALGORITHMIC DEVELOPMENTS

To be adopted by experiments, Acts must provide high quality implementations of classic track reconstruction algorithms. But as a shared toolkit, it is also in an ideal position to serve as an R&D test-bed for the development of new tracking algorithms. During AIDAInnova, progress was made in both areas.

When it comes to algorithmic parity with existing toolkits, AIDAInnova saw the implementation of a Hough transform, a Gaussian sum filter, and a global χ^2 fitter. The quality of implementation of the seeder and Kalman filter was also improved thanks to their integration into the ATLAS ITk chain, which provided useful physics validation and runtime performance optimization feedback.

In terms of new algorithmic developments, one can highlight the following:

- a new k-d tree based seeder, which can provide a 6x improvement in runtime performance over the classic combinatorial approach in HL-LHC conditions;
- an experimental track reconstruction pipeline based on graph neural networks, which was provided by the Exa.TrkX project and then integrated into Acts by AIDAInnova members;
- the introduction of an auto-tuning facility for algorithm parameters, enabled by the new Python API discussed above (presented at ACAT 2022 [5]);
- a new ambiguity solver based on ranking neural networks, which was shown during CHEP 2023 [6] to speed up this duplicate/fake track elimination step by a factor of 15x, while removing 32x more duplicates;
- a new optional filtering stage based on neural networks of a similar architecture was added between track seeding and fitting, which eliminates some fake and duplicate tracks without fitting them, thus reducing the fitting workload by about 2x without significantly affecting physics efficiency (presented at Connecting The Dots 2023 [7]).

3. ACTS GPU AND LINEAR ALGEBRA R&D

3.1. GPU TRACKING

Traditionally, track reconstruction has been mostly performed on CPUs. However, a growing share of available computing power is provided via GPUs. There is therefore growing pressure for HEP codebases to adapt to these processing units.

Early effort to run Acts algorithms on GPUs revealed that some core Acts design decisions, such as the use of a class hierarchy for geometry objects, did not map well to these hardware architectures. This called for R&D around radically different API designs, which could not be carried out within a codebase that is in use by multiple experiments. It was therefore performed in separate repositories, whose organization is quickly described below:

- at the top of the abstraction stack, **traccc** provides a full track reconstruction chain, with three actively developed GPU backends as of 2024: CUDA, SYCL, and Alpaka; a CPU backend is also provided to demonstrate that the approach demonstrated for GPU computing also works well for CPU computations;
- to maximize code sharing across the various traccc backends, **vecmem** abstracts over the various abstractions available to manage CPU and GPU memory in each traccc backend;
- where traccc is mainly concerned with track reconstruction algorithms and the associated event data model, **detrax** takes care of handling detector geometry description and propagation of track parameters through it;
- one subset of the detector description problem, however, is further offloaded from detrax to **covfie**, which takes care of handling the description of a detector's magnetic field;
- underneath traccc and detrax, **algebra-plugin** provides an abstraction layer over several small-matrix linear algebra implementations; this R&D stems from the observation that no known library is very efficient for both CPU and GPU computations.

These projects have all made tremendous progress throughout AIDAinnova. To give some perspective, when the project started, traccc could barely perform hit clustering in pixel detectors using a GPU. While at the time of writing, the CUDA backend is now only missing ambiguity resolution to provide an Acts-like reconstruction chain on the Open Data Detector, and the SYCL backend is not far behind (the main limitation with respect to the CUDA backend being that its Combinatorial Kalman Filter needs further work).

Furthermore, during the last months of the AIDAinnova project, integration of some of these developments back into the main Acts repository has begun. This is hopefully a sign that the split in person-power that was necessary to perform this R&D might soon be coming to an end.

3.2. ADVANCED LINEAR ALGEBRA

The algebra-plugin project was also a good testbed for another R&D evaluation, namely that of alternatives to Eigen. To give context, the Acts project has been using the Eigen library for linear algebra since its inception. However, this library has been known since AIDA2020 to be deeply flawed.

- On CPU, its runtime performance is not competitive. Studying common tracking operations like matrix products, inversions or coordinate transforms from dimension 4 to 8, we found many cases where Eigen is slower than its modern competition by a factor of 2x to 10x.
- On GPU, it is brittle, often failing compilation or silently producing incorrect results.
- Its use of expression templates results in large-scale code duplication, and thus significant compilation-time overhead.
- It is only sporadically maintained, and the highly non-conventional and poorly documented structure of its source code makes it hard for third parties to contribute.

During AIDAInnova, several alternatives to Eigen were evaluated. We found that Fastor was most promising, and therefore made it usable from algebra-plugins. This performance benchmarking and integration effort was reported [8].

Figure 4: Runtime performance of several linear algebra libraries on a small-matrix inversion task [8].

4. MACHINE LEARNING FOR MPGDs

Micro-Patterned Gaseous Detectors (MPGDs) are gaseous detectors with high spatial resolution and good radiation tolerance. They are well-suited for tracking in high background environments, and are thus widely used in current and planned detectors. Among the various available designs, resistive MPGDs provide spark protection, which is important for operational stability.

In AIDAinnova, we specifically concerned ourselves with micro-resistive wells (μ -RWELLS), which are proposed for several upcoming detectors including the LHCb muon upgrade, the EIC cylindrical inner tracker, and the IDEA pre-shower and muon systems at FCC-ee.

Traditional reconstruction algorithms like charge centroid and microTPC guarantee tracking performance over a wide range of particle incidence angles and external magnetic fields, but they break down in the presence of high background. Thus, alternative approaches were investigated.

As a first step, a μ -RWELL simulation was needed. The team started with an existing parametric simulation developed for the BESIII cylindrical GEM detector, implemented a resistive layer, and tuned it using test beam data. This process took longer than expected because COVID-19 significantly and adversely affected detector characterization activities, with detector prototypes shipping late and sometimes in a damaged state. However, the completed work was presented at CHEP 2023 [9].

Figure 5: Comparison of experimental and simulated μ RWELL charge-size relationship

With this, the next step of the AIDAinnova work plan could finally start, namely evaluating new signal cluster reconstruction techniques based on Boosted Decision Trees (BDTs). This evaluation was first performed on the well-understood BESIII CGEM detector, where a promising 12% improvement in signal-to-noise ratio was observed.

Due to test beam delays, evaluation in a μ -RWELL environment has only recently begun. But preliminary results on the IDEA-FCC μ -RWELL detectors suggest a three-fold increase in signal-to-noise ratio. As the detector R&D progresses, this physics performance is expected to improve further, hence AIDAinnova has shown that BDTs will likely prove a powerful technique for IDEA-FCC muon and pre-shower cluster reconstruction and selection.

5. OUTLOOK

Detector technology pioneered by AIDAinnova would not be complete without matching advances in the software that processes the data from all these new detectors.

In the specific context of track reconstruction, one particularly exciting development is the emergence of Acts, which promises to increase code sharing across future HEP experiments. AIDAinnova contributed to this emergence by making the Acts project more sustainable, more readily usable, more feature-complete through new developments that have no equivalent in other contemporary tracking codebases. Many new tracking algorithms are now being designed and integrated first into Acts, which emerges as a leading toolkit for algorithm development and evaluation.

Further down the road, Acts needs to eventually address the growing demand for GPU computing to stay competitive with other track reconstruction codebases. This issue was tackled by the tracc R&D line, which is now reaching its final stages and beginning the long path towards integration into the core Acts toolkit. This paves the way towards a future where Acts will be able to run efficiently on both CPU and GPU, with minimal vendor lock-in and code duplication.

The architectural refactoring associated with this integration may also allow Acts to finally free itself from a deep dependency on the under-par Eigen linear algebra library. AIDAinnova has enabled alternatives to be tested and has selected the most promising one, and making it usable from the Acts GPU R&D stack. However, fully committing to a switch away from Eigen will be difficult and remains as a future challenge.

Finally, AIDAinnova was an occasion to explore new approaches to simulating MPGDs and reconstructing data from them, paving the way towards better μ -RWELL support and increased background tolerance in track reconstruction. This work was most strongly affected by COVID-19 disturbances owing to its high reliance on test beam measurements, and as a result it could not cover its full envisioned scope during the AIDAinnova timeframe. However, significant progress was made, and all expected outcomes are within reach for the future.

All in all, it can be concluded that AIDAinnova task 12.3 was a significant step forward in the area of HEP track reconstruction.

6. REFERENCES

JOURNAL ARTICLES:

- [1] Ai, X. et al (2022) A Common Tracking Software Project, *Computing and Software for Big Science*, 6:8 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41781-021-00078-8>
- [2] Agostinelli, S. et al (2003) Geant4 — a simulation toolkit, *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 506 (3), pp 250-303
- [3] Allison, J. et al (2006) Geant4 developments and applications, *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science*, 53 (1), pp 270-278
- [4] Allison, J. et al (2016) Recent developments in Geant4, *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 835, pp 186-225

CONFERENCE PAPERS

- [5] Allaire, C. et al (2024) Auto-tuning capabilities of the ACTS track reconstruction suite. In: *Proceedings of the 21th International Workshop on Advanced Computing and Analysis Techniques in Physics Research: AI meets Reality*, 23-28 October 2022, Bari, Italy. Online: IOP Conference Series.
- [6] Allaire, C. et al (2024) Ranking-based neural network for ambiguity resolution in ACTS. In: *Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Computing in High Energy and Nuclear Physics (CHEP 2023)*, 8-12 may 2023, Norfolk, USA. Place of publication: EPJ Web of Conf., article 03022.
- [9] Farinelli, R. (2024) PARSIFAL: Parametrized simulation of triple-GEM and micro-RWELL response to a charged particle. In: *Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Computing in High Energy and Nuclear Physics (CHEP 2023)*, 8-12 may 2023, Norfolk, USA. Place of publication: EPJ Web of Conf., article 03028.

WORLD WIDE WEB DOCUMENTS

- [7] Allaire, C. et al (2023) *Seed Finding in the ACTS Software Package - Algorithms and Optimizations* [online]. Available from: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1252748/contributions/5561968/attachments/2731962/4749842/Connecting%20The%20Dots.pdf> [Accessed 11 October 2024].
- [8] Mazmuder, T. (2002) *Acts — Vectorized Linear Algebra Implementation* [online]. Available from: https://hepsoftwarefoundation.org/gsoc/blogs/2022/blog_Acts_TirthankarMazmuder.html [Accessed 11 October 2024].

ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
μ -RWELL	Micro-Resistive Well
BDT	Boosted Decision Tree
CI	Continuous Integration
CPU	Central Processing Unit
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
MPGD	Multi-Patterned Gaseous Detector